

WP3	Deliverable D3.2
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MUSES Project

<p>Title: Stakeholder identification and engagement process in case studies</p>
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MUSES PROJECT

STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION AND ENGAGEMENT PROCESS IN CASE STUDIES

v. 1.1

MUSES DELIVERABLE: D3.2: STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION AND ENGAGEMENT PROCESS IN CASE STUDIES

31 May 2017

Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	5
1.1	<i>Purpose</i>	5
1.2	<i>List of case studies</i>	5
1.3	<i>MUSES approach to stakeholder engagement</i>	8
1.4	<i>WP3 activities: approach to case studies analysis</i>	9
1.5	<i>Methods for stakeholder engagement in WP3 activities</i>	11
2	DESCRIPTION OF STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION AND ENGAGEMENT IN CASE STUDIES	13
2.1	<i>Case study 1: Offshore wind developments coexistence with commercial fisheries / Tidal energy development & environmental interactions</i>	13
2.2	<i>Case study 2: Marine renewables & Aquaculture MU including the use of marine renewable energy near the point of generation</i>	22
2.3	<i>Case study 3: Development of tourism and fishing in the Southern Atlantic Sea</i>	25
2.4	<i>Case study 4: Global resource area optimization, focused on energy, food supply and environment in Swedish waters</i>	29
2.5	<i>Case study 5: Offshore wind production & marine biomass production & environmental remediation in Danish waters</i>	32
2.6	<i>Case study 6: Coastal and Maritime Tourism as a driver/booster for potential multi-use</i>	35
2.7	<i>Case study 7: Tourism & fisheries & energy production in the Aegean Sea</i>	37

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this document is to describe how stakeholder identification and engagement will be carried out at case study level, within work-package 3 (WP3). Actions planned by case study leaders in order to interact with stakeholders are detailed here for each local case study of the MUSES project.

This document complements the MUSES deliverable D3.1 "Case studies" where the methodological approach to WP3 is given and case studies are described in detail, considering their geographical and thematic scope and expected results. However, in order to guarantee the understanding of stakeholder role within WP3, some synthetic elements concerning WP3 activities are also provided in this document.

1.2 List of case studies

Seven case studies are defined for the MUSES project and which will be analysed under WP3. They are listed in Table 1 and represented in Figure 1-1. A detailed description of each case study is provided in chapter 2.

Table 1 - Case studies to be considered under MUSES WP3 activities

Case-study 1	Offshore wind energy developments coexistence with commercial fisheries / Tidal energy development & environmental interactions
Location	North Sea - North Coast of Scotland, East Coast of Scotland and Southern North Sea (German Bight)
Case-study responsible partner	MS
Other participants partners	AWI
Case-study 2	Marine Renewables & Aquaculture MU including the use of marine renewable energy near the point of generation
Location	Northern Atlantic Sea - West Coast of Scotland
Case-study responsible partner	UNIVDUN
Other participants partners	-
Case-study 3	Development of tourism and fishing in the Southern Atlantic Sea
Location	Southern Atlantic Sea: South Coast of mainland Portugal and Azores archipelago
Case-study responsible partner	FGF
Other participants partners	-
Case-study 4	Global resource area optimization, focused on energy, food supply and environment in Swedish waters
Location	Baltic Sea: Island of Gotland (Sweden)
Case-study responsible partner	SUBM
Other participants partners	-
Case-study 5	Offshore wind production & marine biomass production & environmental remediation in Danish waters
Location	Baltic Sea: Southeast Denmark
Case-study responsible partner	SUBM
Other participants partners	-
Case-study 6	Coastal and Maritime Tourism as a driver/booster for potential multi-use
Location	Mediterranean Sea: Northern Adriatic Sea
Case-study responsible partner	ISMAR
Other participants partners	THETIS
Case-study 7	Tourism & fisheries & energy production in the Aegean Sea
Location	Mediterranean Sea: Aegean Sea / Cyclades
Case-study responsible partner	HCMR
Other participants partners	-

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MUSES : MULTI-USE IN EUROPEAN SEAS

Project runs from November 2016 to October 2018

Figure 1-1 Case studies of MUSES project

1.3 MUSES approach to stakeholder engagement

The concepts provided in this paragraph are derived from the MUSES deliverable D2.1 "Analytical framework". Stakeholder analysis methodology has been developed for the purpose of MUSES with an aim to provide understanding of the extent to which stakeholders are affected by, interested in, or could influence/drive the change towards MU. Analysis is set to provide insights on which the stakeholders are behind the identified drivers and barriers.

As a result, this method, which is based on the **Force Field analysis** (FAO, 2013¹), will allow the identification of the barriers that should be addressed by the Action Plan (WP4), as well as stakeholders responsible for implementation of proposed actions. Force Field Analysis is a method for listing, discussing, and evaluating the various forces *for* and *against* a proposed change (Iowa State University, 2017). Force Field Analysis helps systematic analysis of all of the forces impacting the change (in this project Multi-Use) and weighing the opportunities and barriers.

As illustrated in Figure 1-2, Force Field Analysis is based on the premises that change takes place when an imbalance occurs between the sum of the forces against change (Restraining Forces) and the sum of the forces for change (Driving Forces). An imbalance may occur through a change of magnitude or a change in direction in any one of the forces, or through the addition of a new force².

Therefore, the main questions that will be analysed through Force Field method are:

- Does the driving force stand a chance against the restraining force? How can this be changed? Is faster progress feasible?
- Questions about up-scaling driving forces and weakening restraining forces, and how to influence different stakeholders

Knowing who stands behind opportunities and barriers, is necessary for development of strategies to reduce the impact of the opposing forces and strengthen the supporting forces. Force Field Analysis will be used to develop an Action Plan to implement a change. Specifically it will:

1. Determine if a proposed change can get the required support;
2. Identify obstacles to successful solutions, and;
3. Suggest actions to reduce the strength of the obstacles.

This approach will be applied also to analyse results from stakeholder engagement under WP3.

¹ FAO (2013a). *ORGANIZATION ANALYSIS AND DEVELOPMENT*. (D. H. Mariagrazia Rocchigiani, Ed.) Rome, Paris: FAO.

² One should keep in mind that whenever a force changes, other forces might also be influenced (e.g. First movers, tipping points...)

4.

Figure 1-2 Simplified Force Field Analysis diagram for the Offshore Wind Energy (OWE) and aquaculture Multi-Use development

Source: own elaboration SUBMARINER

1.4 WP3 activities: approach to case studies analysis

The objective of MUSES WP3 is to assess potential synergies for Multi-Use as well as the challenges encountered through a series of case studies with different thematic, geographic and focus areas dimension, and to engage with local stakeholders to identify barriers, opportunities, limitation and needs. **The ultimate goal of this analysis is to provide input from a local level scale for the development of an Action Plan for MU under WP4.**

Case studies will be developed both through desk activities of review and analysis and stakeholder involvement. Desk analysis and stakeholder engagement activities will be combined but the process will be in a large part stakeholder-oriented: stakeholder knowledge, experience and perception will constitute the most relevant part of the analysis. Methodology and tools to be applied in case-study analysis are detailed in the MUSES deliverable D3.1.

Desk activities will examine legislative and administrative documents at national/local level, plans, projects, studies, scientific papers etc. Results will inform stakeholder engagement activities.

Stakeholders at a local level will be engaged with the scope of discussing views, options and opinions on MU development / strengthening at local scale.

As described in Figure 2-1, the methodology for case study analysis consists of two phases:

- Phase A. Case study Implementation (Task 3.2)
- Phase B. Comparative analysis (Task 3.3).

In “Phase A - Case study Implementation” five steps can be identified, as follows:

1. MU overview & identification of potentials
2. Identification of MU drivers, barriers, added value, impacts
3. Analysis of MU potentials

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4. Evaluation of overall MU net effect
5. Analysis by Focus Areas (see D3.1, chapter 2.1.5 for specifications).

In “Phase B - Comparative analysis” three themes will be considered:

1. analysis of overall MU potentials and effects
2. analysis by Focus Areas
3. paired case-study analysis.

Stakeholders will be involved in all steps of Phase A. Both Phase A and Phase B will generate outputs which are illustrated in Figure 1-3 below.

Figure 1-3 Graphical flow chart of the case study methodology and expected outputs

1.3 Stakeholder role in WP3 activities

As stated in the previous paragraph, stakeholders will be involved in all steps of Phase A. Particularly, **under Steps 2-3-4**, a number of relevant factors will be identified by case study leaders during desk analysis, with reference to the four themes of DABI: Drivers, Barriers, Added Value and Impact. The

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catalogue of factors and their related descriptions will provide a background knowledge-base for interacting with the stakeholders. The factors identified during the desk analysis will then be evaluated and scored by stakeholders during interviews, workshops or any of the other consultation methods implemented in WP3. Stakeholder scores will provide a picture of perceived DABI of MU. The overall process is described in Figure 1-3. In addition, experts and stakeholders will be asked to identify additional factors according to their knowledge/experience. Details about this process are given in the MUSES deliverable D3.1.

Under Step 5 stakeholders will contribute to analysis of Focus Areas by providing case study leaders with elements in order to answer set of Key Evaluation Questions (KEQs), in relation to each case study. The definitions of Focus Areas and the list of Key Evaluation Questions are also given in the MUSES deliverable D3.1. Draft answers to KEQs will be prepared by case study leaders based on knowledge and information collected during the desk phase of the research. Questions and draft answers will be proposed to local stakeholder for verification / modification / integration during workshops and/or interviews. Introductory statements on MU and DABI will be required when approaching stakeholders in the survey part of the work, in order to make sure that the offset for the survey is comparable. Based on stakeholder feedback the final version of the answers will be prepared by CS leader considering outcomes from all interviews and/or integrating results of workshop discussion.

Figure 1-4 Diagram of the evaluation methodology of MU in Sea Basins and Case-Studies.

Source: own elaboration by THETIS

1.5 Methods for stakeholder engagement in WP3 activities

Stakeholder engagement will be implemented according to the specific characteristics and needs of each case study. Nevertheless, in order to ensure comparability, all case studies will implement some of the following engagement methods:

- a) **Interviews** for collecting stakeholder input on MU potential, MU possible combinations, evaluation of drivers/barriers to MU and added value/impact of MU.

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- b) **Expert panel(s)** (5-10 persons) for identification and assessment of proposed MUs. The panel(s) will identify opportunities, validate proposals, identify synergies, highlight drivers/barriers to MU, discuss added values/impacts of MU, propose policy recommendations to overcome such barriers.
- c) **Local workshop(s)** (15-25 persons) for consultation with local stakeholders and administrative authorities. The workshop(s) will be organized to identify potential conflicts both among sectors and between proposed activities and local planning, to explore proper integration of proposed co-location activities to local economic structure, to prepare recommendations by local stakeholders and administrative authorities for coping with conflicts. Drivers/barriers and added values/impacts of MUs will be also evaluated.
- d) **Consensus conference(s)** (10-30 persons) for consultation with local society. The conference(s) will address discussion after presentation from the case study group to open the whole process to inhabitants, in order to widen dissemination of information and to prepare recommendations for local community groups on the proposed co-location of sea activities. Drivers/barriers and added values/impacts of MUs will be also discussed.
- e) Other engagement processes may be utilised as the project progresses and as required.

Detailed description of stakeholder engagement methods for each of the case studies is reported in chapter 2.

2 DESCRIPTION OF STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION AND ENGAGEMENT IN CASE STUDIES

Stakeholder identification and engagement will be carried out in the seven case studies that will be considered by MUSES project, under WP3 activities. Details on stakeholder identification and engagement at the case study level are described in the following look-up tables.

2.1 *Case study 1: Offshore wind developments coexistence with commercial fisheries / Tidal energy development & environmental interactions*

This case study considers three sub-cases, referring to different geographical areas and MU combinations. They are:

- sub-case-study 1-a: Multi-Use of sea between commercial fisheries and offshore wind farms in Scotland (East coast of Scotland)
- sub-case-study 1-b: Tidal Energy Development and Environmental Interactions (North coast of Scotland)
- sub-case-study 1-c: Multi-use of offshore wind farm (OWF) areas with (A) fisheries and (B) aquaculture (C) and restoration efforts (Southern North Sea, German Bight)

Stakeholder identification and engagement in the sub-case studies are described hereafter.

1. Case study n. 1-a
2. Regional Sea: North Sea
3. Location: East Coast of Scotland
4. Title: Multi-use space between commercial fisheries and offshore wind farms in Scotland
5. Case-Study area:

6. Stakeholder identification:

We have identified and listed a number of stakeholders for this case study below, this list may be subject to change once the work on the case study commences and potentially other relevant stakeholders are identified. It will also be important to liaise with the Case Study 2 leader as there is potential for overlap in the stakeholders that we would like to consult:

Offshore Wind Energy developers

Offshore Wind Farm Energy Developers (and respective representative energy companies) who have submitted a marine licence application to the Scottish marine licencing competent authority (Marine Scotland – Licence Operations Team; MS-LOT) in the East Coast of Scotland have been identified as relevant for the MUSES Case Study 1 and includes:

- Beatrice Offshore Windfarm Limited (BOWL), incl. Scottish and Southern Energy (SSE) Renewables
- Moray Offshore Windfarm Limited (MORL), incl. Energias de Portugal (EDP) Renovavels and Repsol
- SeaGreen Wind Energy Limited, incl. Scottish and Southern Energy (SSE) Renewables
- Inch Cape Offshore Limited, incl. Red Rock Power Ltd
- Neart na Gaoithe (NNG) Offshore Wind Limited, incl. Mainstream Renewable Power
- Forthwind Limited, incl. 2-B Energy UK
- Kincardine Offshore Windfarm Limited (KOWL), incl. Atkins Ltd. And MacAskill Associates
- Hywind Scotland Pilot Park, incl. Statoil Wind Limited (SWL)

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Commercial fisheries representation bodies

Non-statutory consultees with commercial fisheries interests, who have submitted a response to the statutory consultation exercise performed by MS-LOT for offshore wind farm developments found above, have been identified as relevant for this MUSES Case Study 1. Stakeholders were listed in the Consultation Exercise Section, Annex B:

Background Information and Scottish Ministers’ considerations, of the [‘Submission to Ministers’](#) for each development project, and are listed below:

- Scottish Fishermen’s Federation (SFF)
- Scottish Inshore Fisheries Groups (IFGs), incl. East Coast Inshore Fisheries Group
- The Scallop Association (SA)
- Fife Fishermen’s Mutual Association
- Firth of Forth 10 Metre and Under Association (10MUA)
- The Inshore Fishermen’s Alliance (IFA)
- Arbroath and Montrose Static Gear Association (AMSGA)
- Firth of Forth Lobster Hatchery (FoFLH)

Table 1: Consultation responses by commercial fisheries organisations for East coast of Scotland offshore wind energy developments

	BOWL	MORL	SeaGreen	Inch Cape	NNG	Forthwind	KOWL	Hywind
SFF								
IFGs								
Scallop Association								
Fife Fishermen’s Mutual Association								
10 Metre and Under Association								
IFA								
Arbroath and Montrose Static Gear Association								
Firth of Forth Lobster Hatchery								

National Organisations

- The Fishing Liaison with Offshore Wind and Wet Renewables Group (FLOWW), including The Crown Estate (TCE)

7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders:

Issues to be discussed with stakeholders, in order to collect their knowledge, experience and perceptions, include:

- Policy and industry drivers for facilitating coexistence between the two industries
- Potential sources of conflicts between offshore wind farm developments and commercial

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fisheries, also referred to as barriers. For example, these include loss of access to fishing grounds, displacement of the fishing activity to alternative fishing locations etc.

- Potential economic, environmental, and social consequences of conflicts, also known as impacts (negative effects). For example, loss of earnings, overfishing, loss of local knowledge etc.
- Management interventions taken/ further needed to mitigate impacts (negative effects), and
- Resulting synergies and added value from Multi-use

8. Stakeholder engagement methods:
 Engagement methods relevant to this case study include:

- Semi-structured interviews, as well as
- Conventional presentations and feedback from expert panels/ conferences

As development of the web platform progresses, the case study will consider the sharing of information material with local stakeholders. We will seek to sign up the stakeholders to our Project newsletter and provide them with advice on where they can get more information on the MUSES project.

9. Details on stakeholder engagement:

Interviews:
 Relevant stakeholders have been preliminary identified in Section 6. Key stakeholders will be engaged using one-on-one interviews to identify key barriers and formulate strategies to overcome them. Where possible we will conduct face to face interviews with the stakeholders at a time that is convenient for the stakeholders. We will, however, attempt to have ‘back to back’ interviews with stakeholders that are in the same geographical location to reduce the costs and time for travelling. As a last resort, GoToMeeting online platform or telephone interviews will be conducted. Interviews with key stakeholders will be conducted during the mid and end period of the case study with approximately 10 stakeholders.

Expert panels:
 Expert panel(s) from representative bodies (e.g. SFF’s Board of Directors, FLOWW working group) will be opportunistically targeted to identify the key barriers and opportunities for Multi Use. Expert panels will be preferred over one-to-one interviews in an effort to overcome individual views.

10. Expected results and impacts:

- Scotland’s National Marine Plan and other key national policy documents
- National and European directives, e.g. MSP Directive
- National stakeholder forums, e.g. UK Working Group on Fisheries Liaison with Offshore Wind and Wet Renewables Group (FLOWW).
- Scientific and grey literature
- Past European projects, e.g. CO-EXISTENCE

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1. Case study n. 1-b
2. Regional Sea: North Sea
3. Location: North Coast of Scotland / Inner Sound of the Pentland Firth
4. Title: Tidal Energy Development and Environmental Interactions
5. Case-Study area:

6. Stakeholder identification:

We have identified and listed a number of potential stakeholders for this case study below, this list may be subject to change once the work on the case study commences and potentially other relevant stakeholders are identified. It will also be important to liaise with the Case Study 2 leader as there is potential for overlap in the stakeholders that we would like to consult:

Private Companies

- MeyGen – Tidal Renewable Energy
- DP Energy – Tidal Renewable Energy
- Openhydro - Tidal Renewable Energy

National Organisations

- Atlantic Salmon Trust
- Fisheries Management Scotland
- Joint Nature Conservation Committee
- Marine Scotland
- Scottish Environment Link
- Scottish Natural Heritage
- Scottish Renewables

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<p>Local level European Marine Energy Centre Orkney Islands Council The Highland Council</p> <p>Academic International Centre for Island Technology (ICIT) (Heriot Watt) MASTS Scottish Association of Marine Science (SAMS) Sea Mammals Research Unit – St Andrews University University of Aberdeen University of the Highlands & Islands.</p>
<p>7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders: We have selected a diverse range of stakeholders that have experience of Marine Renewable Energy projects, environmental issues, academic institutions dealing with relevant research, local councils and Marine Scotland officials that had input to the Pilot Pentland Firth & Orkney Waters Marine Spatial Plan as well as Marine Scotland staff that have relevant planning, licensing and research experience. We believe that this mix of stakeholders will allow us to gather information on drivers, barriers, added values and impacts. Once these are established we hope to explore how to overcome and minimise barriers and maximise the benefits, as well as how to best promote Blue Growth whilst protecting the marine environment and/or minimising impacts. In particular we will focus the study around the interactions of tidal energy generation with the environment including wild salmon and marine mammals and the identification of technical solutions to minimise environmental impact.</p>
<p>8. Stakeholder engagement methods: We anticipate that the main method of engagement with stakeholders will be by interview. Where possible we will conduct face to face interviews with the stakeholders at a time that is convenient for the stakeholders. We will, however, attempt to have ‘back to back’ interviews with stakeholders that are in the same geographical location to reduce the costs and time for travelling. We will consider co-ordination, with the Case Study 2 leader on how we can best deal with any stakeholders that may be in common to both cases study 1 and 2.</p>
<p>9. Details on stakeholder engagement: Interviews will be arranged with the stakeholders at a time that is convenient for them. We will, however, attempt to have ‘back to back’ interviews with stakeholders that are in the same geographical location to reduce the costs and time for travelling. Other methods such as teleconferencing, Go-To-Meetings or Skype may be used if appropriate and to reduce costs.</p>
<p>10. Expected results and impacts: The case study objectives are to explore the interactions of tidal energy generation with the environment particularly with marine mammals and wild salmon. This will provide us with an understanding of the multi-use/coexistence and the associated drivers, barriers, added values and impacts. Gathering this information will, we hope, assist in the identification of technical solutions to minimise environmental impact. We will seek to sign up the stakeholders to our Project newsletter and provide them with advice on where they can get more information on the MUSES project. The case study analysis will ultimately be passed across to work-package 4 and under the ‘Action Plan’ it will be utilised with other project information to present a vision highlighting real opportunities for MU in European Seas including scope for innovation and Blue Growth potential. The Action plan will suggest solutions to overcome and reduce potential barriers and impacts to multi-use in European seas. The ‘Data Management Plan (DMP)’ prepared under the work of WP5 outlines how data will be</p>

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handled both during the MUSES project and after the project is completed. The processes outlined in the DMP will assist improving and maximising access to and re-use of research data generated by the MUSES project.

1. Case study n. 1-c
2. Regional Sea: North Sea
3. Location: Southern North Sea, German Bight / German EEZ
4. Title: Multi-use of offshore wind farm (OWF) areas with (A) fisheries and (B) aquaculture (C) and restoration efforts
5. Case-Study area:

6. Stakeholder identification:

1) Identified stakeholders are from the categories:

- Commercial fisheries
- Governance
- Environment
- Offshore Wind Energy
- Aquaculture
- Academic/Research
- Other

2) The preliminary number of stakeholders identified and sent to Marine Scotland to be incorporated into the Stakeholder Master List is 92. This number is going to change as the case study develops. Not all stakeholders identified will be contacted, rather key stakeholders out of the whole network will be identified and engaged.

7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders:

As part of previous projects conducted in the case study area of the German Bight, multiple stakeholder workshops have already been conducted and drivers and barriers of multi-use of resources identified. Future discussions with stakeholders within the scope of MUSES will focus on those drivers and barriers of multi-use that were previously identified to help formulate concrete

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strategies which will help to tackle and overcome those barriers. For a short summary of those, please see the description provided for this case study in D3.1.

8. Stakeholder engagement methods:

The following engagement methods will be used:

- 1) interviews
- 2) expert panels
- 3) local workshops.

For description and further elaboration on the engagement methods please refer to section 9.

At this point no dissemination of results via the planned MUSES platform in WP5 is planned. As development of the web platform progresses however and means and opportunities become apparent, the sharing of information material with local stakeholders via the platform may be adopted.

9. Details on stakeholder engagement:

Interviews:

Key stakeholders will be identified via a complete stakeholder mapping and analysis of the case study area. Those key stakeholders will be engaged using one-on-one interviews to identify key barriers and formulate strategies to overcome them. Interviews with key stakeholders will be conducted during the mid and end period of the case study with approximately 10 stakeholders.

Expert panels:

Expert panel(s) or focus groups will be conducted in preparation for a local workshop. These focus groups, made up of key stakeholders from individual sectors, will serve to identify the key issues to be discussed at local workshops. Up to 3 expert panels will be conducted leading up to the main stakeholder workshop with representatives of key industries and regulatory bodies.

Local workshops:

A local stakeholder workshop will only be conducted if new information regarding the stakeholders surfaces during the elaboration of the case study. This will help to keep local stakeholders interested and not oversaturate them with information. This workshop will build on the observations and advice generated by focus groups and prepare recommendations building on the expert knowledge of invited stakeholders while simultaneously informing them of relevant new insights and developments on the subject matter. The local workshop will be conducted close to the end of the case study period to present the stakeholders with new findings on barriers, drivers, added value and possible negative impacts. It will also serve to formulate a combined regional strategy to overcome those identified barriers that will contribute to the efforts of WP4.

10. Expected results and impacts:

This case study stands apart from many others in that it builds on an established knowledge base on the feasibility of offshore multi-use. This knowledge base has been built in co-operation with local and national stakeholders interested in the topic during many previous projects and workshops. As such, this case study will use a very targeted approach to selecting specific key stakeholders for interviews so as to not duplicate previous work and oversaturate stakeholders with requests for information. Many of the stakeholders that will be involved in this case study are already part of an existing informal network and the work undertaken here will work to better connect that network and allow for future collaborations.

The chosen interviews will elaborate and build on the already identified drivers, added value, barriers and impacts to identify the best approach to overcoming the identified barriers. These approaches will then directly feedback up into WPs 4 & 5.

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2.2 Case study 2: Marine renewables & Aquaculture MU including the use of marine renewable energy near the point of generation

1. Case study n. 2
2. Regional Sea: Atlantic Sea
3. Location: Northern Atlantic Sea - West Coast of Scotland
4. Title: Marine Renewables & Aquaculture MU including the use of marine renewable energy near the point of generation
5. Study area:

6. Stakeholder identification:

We have already identified more than 25 stakeholders that can be of interest for the engagement process in our case study, especially from the Multi-Use perspective. These are mainly regional, national and local stakeholders interested in, impacted by, and located in Scottish West Coast. They range from decision-makers, private companies to research centres.

For the selected case study, harmonisation with the Eastern Atlantic group (case study 1-a) will be useful, for synergies and cost-effective use of engagement resources and to avoid engaging the same stakeholders in work package 4.

Regional

- Aquaculture Advisory Council
- Beyond Energy Action Strategies
- European Marine Energy Centre

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National level

- Anglo Scottish Fishermen’s Association - Commercial fisheries – WP3&4
- Association of Scottish Shellfish Growers – Commercial Fisheries
- Atlantic Salmon Trust – Recreational Fisheries
- British Marine Federation
- British Ports Association
- British Trout Association
- CoSLA – SLAED – Tourism Officials
- Defence Infrastructure Organisation (DIO)
- Fishermen’s Association Ltd
- Greenpeace
- Institute of Estuarine and Coastal Studies- Research – WP3&4
- Joint Nature Conservation Committee– WP3&4
- Marine Management Organisation– WP3&4
- National Grid– WP3&4
- North Atlantic Fisheries College– WP3&4
- Oil & Gas UK– WP3&4
- Salmon and Trout Conservation Scotland -WP2,3&4
- Scottish Environment Protection Agency- WP2,3&4
- Scottish Fishermen's Federation - WP2,3&4

Local level

- Argyll and Bute Council – WP2,3&4
- Clyde Fishermen’s Association– WP2,3&4
- Moray Firth and North East Inshore Fishery Group– WP2,3&4
- Orkney management Group – Commercial fisheries– WP2,3&4
- Outer Hebrides Inshore Fishery Group– Commercial fisheries– WP2,3&4

Private companies

- AlbaTERN Ltd - Marine Renewables energy – Tidal – WP3&4
- Blue Energy - Marine Renewables energy – Tidal – WP3&4
- Bluewater Energy Services B.V - Marine Renewables energy – Tidal – WP3&4
- Carbon-Clean technologies
- DP Energy - Marine Renewables energy - Tidal
- EDPR (MORL) – Offshore Energy

7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders:
 Stakeholders will provide us with information about the existing and potential MU and the identification of drivers, barriers, added values and impacts. We will collect as much information as possible in a single interview, taking advantage of the knowledge and expertise of the stakeholders to be interviewed. Even if we have identified some MU and DABI information during our desk research they will validate the information.

8. Stakeholder engagement methods:
 The method of engagement we will use is structured interviews that will allow us to identify existing and potential MU in our study area and evaluate drivers, barriers, added values and impacts for MU. Interviews might be recorded and analysed subsequently.

9. Details on stakeholder engagement:
 Interviews will be in person where possible. When travelling costs are high interviews will be made by teleconference, using Go to Meeting or Skype software. Interviews will be developed mainly in

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English.

10. Expected results and impacts:

We expect to have a clear picture and characterisation of the existing and potential MU as well as drivers, barriers, added values and impacts associated to them in our case study. Stakeholder engagement is a key phase to check and validate the information collected during the desk analysis. Stakeholders will benefit from the case study analysis and the results of the project, especially from the Action Plan (WP4), which might serve as basis to develop key recommendations for the Scottish and UK Governments to overcome identified barriers and negative impacts, as well as promote existing drivers and added values for MU.

2.3 Case study 3: Development of tourism and fishing in the Southern Atlantic Sea

- 1. Case study n. 3
- 2. Regional Sea: Atlantic Sea
- 3. Location: Southern Atlantic Sea: South Coast of mainland Portugal and Azores archipelago
- 4. Title: Development of tourism and fishing in the Southern Atlantic Sea
- 5. Study area:

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6. Stakeholder identification:

We have already identified more than 40 stakeholders that can be of interest for the engagement process and/or for disseminating information in our case study. From this list the more relevant targets will be identified from the Multi-Use perspective. These will be mainly regional and local stakeholders located in both the Algarve and Azores regions. They range from decision-makers, private companies to research centres. The list of stakeholders will be a live document, subject to changes and adaptations while the case study implementation goes on.

There will be a few stakeholders with emphasis on both regions:

- Portuguese General Directorate for Maritime Policy (DGPM)
- Portuguese General Directorate for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services (DGRM)
- Navy

Algarve region:

- Tunipex Empresa de Pesca de Tunídeos, S.A. (farming/commercial fisheries)
- Tuna Dive Tours (recreational activities)
- Centro de Investigação Marinha e Ambiental (environment/cross-cutting-academia)
- Região de Turismo do Algarve (tourism)

Azores region:

- Direção Regional da Cultura (cultural heritage)
- Direção Regional do Turismo (tourism)
- Octopus, Actividades Náuticas Lda (recreational activities)
- Pescadores de Nordeste (commercial fisheries)
- YouSeaMe (recreational activities)
- Direção Regional dos Assuntos do Mar (cross-cutting)

7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders:

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Stakeholders will provide us with information about the existing and potential MU and the identification of drivers, barriers, added values and impacts. We will collect as much as information as possible in a single interview, taking advantage of the knowledge and expertise of the stakeholders to be interviewed. Even if we have identified some MU and DABI information during our desk research they will validate the information.

8. Stakeholder engagement methods:

Interviews will be the main engagement method. The method will consist of individual structured interviews which will follow the case-study sheets as the main interview supporting documents. The interviews will be conducted with a sample of representative individuals from different stakeholder groups: public authorities, scientists, sector operators, investors, local representatives of economic sectors or local communities. This method will allow the identification of existing and potential MU in the study area and evaluate drivers, barriers, added values and impacts for MU.

Out of the few possible methods to involve stakeholders, interviews were considered as the preferable method to gather the information needed for case study 3. Interviews indeed are an excellent method of gaining access to information about experiences and opinions and help to fill the gaps in knowledge that other methods are unable to bridge (Dunn 2005). Individual interviews are moreover highly effective at generating items in a brainstorming task (Guest et al. 2017). As Pomeroy and Douvere (2008) stated, conducting interviews is a comprehensive and efficient manner to collect data on stakeholders and their attributes, being the participatory research approach the working method most commonly used in the field of stakeholder analysis and is considered as the best method for a successful outcome.

9. Details on stakeholder engagement:

Interviews will be in person where possible. When travelling costs are high interviews will be made by teleconference, using Go to Meeting or Skype software. Interviews will be developed either in Portuguese or in English, if necessary.

Interviews will orderly go one by one through the list of case-study fiches which have been previously filled with the identified MU and the factors catalogue (on drivers, barriers, added values and (negative) impacts) during the desk research phase. The interview will be supported by complementary documents like the map fiche, besides the consenting form. Interviews will ask respondents in a first phase to:

- discuss and identify new drivers/barriers and added values/impacts of MU;
- evaluate and score factors for drivers, barriers, added values and impacts.
- discuss answers to key evaluation questions identified for each focus areas.

The process of interviewing will follow the following steps (when possible):

- Record: interviews will be recorded mainly with specialised software (i.e. Amolto Call Recorder);
- Notes: taken during and immediately after the interview to express the impressions about the interview and the important points from the interviewer perspective;
- Transcription: interviews will be transcribed from the recording device and the notes taken;
- Interpretation: reduce the data collected to the essential for WP3 goals;
- Reporting: integrate the relevant information obtained from the interview in a general report on stakeholder engagement for the case-study.

10. Expected results and impacts:

We expect to have a clear picture and characterisation of the existing and potential MU as well as drivers, barriers, added values and impacts associated to them in our case study. Stakeholder engagement is a key phase to check and validate the information collected during the desk analysis. Stakeholders will benefit from the case study analysis and the results of the project, especially from the Action Plan (WP4), which might serve as basis to develop key recommendations for the

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Portuguese and Azorean Governments to overcome identified barriers and negative impacts, as well as promote existing drivers and added values for MU.

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2.4 Case study 4: Global resource area optimization, focused on energy, food supply and environment in Swedish waters

- 1. Case study n. 4
- 2. Regional Sea: Baltic Sea
- 3. Location: Baltic Sea: Island of Gotland (Sweden)
- 4. Title: Global resource area optimization, focused on energy, food supply and environment in Swedish waters
- 5. Study area:

- 6. Stakeholder identification:**
- 1) The categories of stakeholders to be engaged:
 - national and local authorities responsible for licensing and marine management
 - offshore wind farm operators,
 - development agencies,
 - tourist organisations,
 - aquaculture operators,
 - fishing and tourism societies and local business organisations.
 - local environmental protection agencies,
 - NGOs and civil organisations representing local society and their activities.
 - 2) Between 15 -20 stakeholders
 - 3) preliminary list of stakeholders: Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management, Ministry of Environment and Energy Regeringskansliet, Region Gotland, Länsstyrelsen i Gotlands län (Gotland County Administration), Samförvaltningsinitiativet Gotland (Gotland Co-management initiative), Yrkesfiskarna/Professional fishermen, Öland-Gotlands Fiskareförbund (Öland-Gotland Fishermen's Association), Momentum Gruppen A/S, OM O2, DONG Energy, E.ON.

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7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders:

The keys issues that we are intending to discuss with stakeholders includes the following:

- Barriers and drivers concerning multi-use; collection of knowledge regarding the lack of tradition for cooperation between the different sectors, expert judgement regarding possible conflict of interests, motivation for collaboration, identification of remediation sites vs wind sites and practical challenges of multi-use.
- Barriers concerning establishment of mariculture - knowledge and expertise gathering regarding the opinions about seaweed and mussel farming in Swedish waters
- Barriers concerning legal licences, permits and insurance – gathering of knowledge, expertise and expert judgement
- Drivers for reducing eutrophication; nutrient remediation and positive environmental added value, potentials for a local blue bio-economy – synergies with local development strategies, considerations regarding nature preservation and biodiversity in the local marine environment
- Barriers and drivers for relevant stakeholder involvement – gathering experience and expertise regarding the challenges and motivation for establishing mariculture, financial, legal and practical challenges from the local perspective.

8. Stakeholder engagement methods:

- a) Interviews for collecting stakeholder input on MU potential, MU possible combinations, evaluation of drivers/barriers to MU and added value/impact of MU
- b) Expert panel(s) (5-10 persons) for identification and assessment of proposed MUs. The panel(s) will identify opportunities, validate proposals, create synergies, highlight drivers/barriers to MU, discuss added values/impacts of MU, propose policy recommendations to overcome such barriers. (this might be an option - TBD)
- c) Local workshop(s) (15-25 persons) for consultation with local stakeholders and administrative authorities. The workshop(s) will be organized to identify potential conflicts both among sectors and between proposed activities and local planning, to explore proper integration of proposed co-location activities to local economic structure, to prepare recommendations by local stakeholders and administrative authorities for coping with conflicts. Drivers/barriers and added values/impacts of MUs will be also evaluated.
- d) Interactive webinars might be used as means to include the wider share of stakeholders and validate research results.
- e) Questionnaires might also be used for collecting information from stakeholders

9. Details on stakeholder engagement:

- TBD - Local workshop back to back with Almedalsveckan/Almedalen Week July 2 - July 9, 2017. Almedalsveckan/Almedalen Week is a yearly event when lobbyists, local and national politicians, employees from local, regional and national organisations and representatives of non-governmental organizations all coming to Visby to meet, discuss politics and socialize.
- TBD – Expert panel back to back with Life Under Water conference 11 Oct - 13 Oct 2017, The City of Malmö is in collaboration with KIMO and WMU organizing the Life Under Water conference.
- TBD – Interviews with tourism sector (researchers, government employees, industry practitioners) on 13-16 June International Congress on Coastal and Marine Tourism 2017 in the city of Gothenburg, Sweden.

10. Expected results and impacts:

With this case study, we hope to open the dialogue between the stakeholders that can potentially benefit from a geographical and biological multi-use of an existing offshore wind park and identify how to overcome the barriers that are hindering what, potentially, contribute to food supply in

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Island of Gotland and significant reduction of environmental impacts in the surrounding Baltic Sea. We will encourage the stakeholders to affiliate with the existing network, SUBMARINER EEIG, where they can find a network of institutions and organisations that are relevant for their interest in development of the Baltic Sea.

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2.5 Case study 5: Offshore wind production & marine biomass production & environmental remediation in Danish waters

1. Case study n. 5

2. Regional Sea: Baltic Sea

3. Location: South Baltic Sea – South Coast of Lolland-Falster - Rødsand

4. Title: Offshore wind and mariculture; potentials for multi-use and nutrient remediation in Rødsand 2

5. Study area:

6. Stakeholder identification:

1. Energy providers, Branch Organisations, local island networks and fishermen, business development agencies, tourist organisations, national authorities, local government, NGOs
2. Between 15 – 20 stakeholders
3. DONG Energy, E.ON, SEAS-NVE, Danish Aquaculture, Danish Small Islands network, Business Lolland-Falster, Visit Lolland-Falster, Danish Energy Authority, Lolland and Guldborgsund Municipalities, Danish Nature Preservation Association

7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders:

The keys issues that we are intending to discuss with stakeholders includes the following:

- Barriers and drivers concerning co-localisation; collection of knowledge regarding the lack of tradition for cooperation between the different sectors, expert judgement regarding possible conflict of interests, motivation for collaboration, identification of remediation sites vs wind sites and practical challenges of co-existence at sea.
- Barriers concerning establishment of mariculture; Danish Water Framework Directive – state of play concerning aquaculture: limitations, definitions, environmental considerations – knowledge and expertise gathering regarding the opinions about seaweed and mussel

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- farming in Danish waters
- Barriers concerning legal licences, permits and insurance – gathering of knowledge, expertise and expert judgement
- Drivers for reducing eutrophication; nutrient remediation and positive environmental added value, potentials for a local blue bio-economy – synergies with local development strategies, considerations regarding nature preservation and biodiversity in the local marine environment
- Barriers and drivers for relevant stakeholder involvement – gathering experience and expertise regarding the challenges and motivation for establishing mariculture off the southern coast of Lolland, financial, legal and practical challenges from the local perspective.

8. Stakeholder engagement methods:

- a) Interviews for collecting stakeholder input on MU potential, MU possible combinations, evaluation of drivers/barriers to MU and added value/impact of MU
- b) Expert panel(s) (5-10 persons) for identification and assessment of proposed MUs. The panel(s) will identify opportunities, validate proposals, create synergies, highlight drivers/barriers to MU, discuss added values/impacts of MU, propose policy recommendations to overcome such barriers.
- c) Local workshop(s) (15-25 persons) for consultation with local stakeholders and administrative authorities. The workshop(s) will be organized to identify potential conflicts both among sectors and between proposed activities and local planning, to explore proper integration of proposed co-location activities to local economic structure, to prepare recommendations by local stakeholders and administrative authorities for coping with conflicts. Drivers/barriers and added values/impacts of MUs will be also evaluated.

9. Details on stakeholder engagement:

- a) Interviews for collecting stakeholder input on MU potential, MU possible combinations, evaluation of drivers/barriers to MU and added value/impact of MU
 - i. Personal interviews with specific targeted stakeholders regarding the Rødsand 2 wind park.
 - ii. Folkemødet, Bornholm – 17th/18th June 2017 – Denmark’s annual gathering of local and national politicians and business stakeholders will give us the opportunity to gather a broader social feedback regarding the employment of MU in combination of Danish offshore infrastructures.
- b) Expert panel(s) (5-10 persons) for identification and assessment of proposed MUs. The panel(s) will identify opportunities, validate proposals, create synergies, highlight drivers/barriers to MU, discuss added values/impacts of MU, propose policy recommendations to overcome such barriers.
 - i. EUBSR Strategy – Workshop, Berlin 13th June 2017 (TBD)
- c) Local workshop(s) (15-25 persons) for consultation with local stakeholders and administrative authorities. The workshop(s) will be organized to identify potential conflicts both among sectors and between proposed activities and local planning, to explore proper integration of proposed co-location activities to local economic structure, to prepare recommendations by local stakeholders and administrative authorities for coping with conflicts. Drivers/barriers and added values/impacts of MUs will be also evaluated.
 - i. Date not fixed yet – in collaboration with local government

10. Expected results and impacts:
 With this case study, we hope to open the dialogue between the stakeholders that can potentially benefit from a geographical and biological multi-use of an existing offshore wind park (in this case, Rødsand 2) and identify how to overcome the barriers that are hindering what, potentially, could be part of the basis for a new blue bio-economy on Lolland-Falster and a significant reduction of

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environmental impacts in the surrounding Baltic Sea.
We will encourage the stakeholders to affiliate with the existing network, SUBMARINER EEIG, where they can find a network of institutions and organisations that are relevant for their interest in development of the Baltic Sea.

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2.6 Case study 6: Coastal and Maritime Tourism as a driver/booster for potential multi-use

1. Case study n. 6

2. Regional Sea: Mediterranean Sea

3. Location: Mediterranean Sea: Northern Adriatic Sea

4. Title: Coastal and Maritime Tourism as a driver/booster for potential multi-use

5. Study area:

6. Stakeholder identification:

For the case study, about 20 stakeholders will be considered including decision makers (local/regional and national level) and from different sectors (energy, fishery, aquaculture, environmental protection, tourism and research). The following preliminary list of stakeholders is identified:

- Veneto and Emilia-Romagna regions (Decision making/Planning)
- Ministry of Economic Development (Decision maker)
- Polo Offshore di Ravenna (Research/Planning)
- ENI (Energy)
- Associazione Mediterranea Acquacoltori (Aquaculture)
- Ca' Foscari University (Research)
- Regional fishery associations (Fishery)
- Others tbd

Along with the stakeholder identification process, other referential stakeholders on national level and from Veneto and Emilia-Romagna regions will be screened, identified and, if required, involved in the overall stakeholder engagement strategy.

7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders:

The key issues to be analysed in this case study will include the driving factors and the barriers

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related to multi-use development as well as the added value and potential negative impact of its establishment, in order to contribute to WP4 and the definition of the Action Plan.

A desk research study will be performed to set the baseline information, followed by interviews with stakeholders and a workshop to discuss preliminary results. Technical aspects (e.g. methods and tools for data analysis) are also essential for the implementation of the MU.

The involvement and an active discussion with key stakeholders will be fundamental for a concrete and shared vision towards MU in the area, starting from a re-analysis of the multi-use potential in the area, to confirm or correct/integrate the preliminary vision.

8. Stakeholder engagement methods:

Interviews will be based on the prior desk research, identifying the DABI on local/regional/national scale for the specific case study level MUs. Stakeholders interviews will then complement the desk analysis and will be divided into two stages. Stage 1 is focused on the compilation of the Analytical Framework (AF) sheets together with the stakeholders, this will encompass the definition of scope conditions for potentials MUs on case study level. In stage 2, the compilation of DABI will progress to factor scorings, which will be operated using remote means of communications, such as telephone and teleconference.

In the interview stage, stakeholders will be informed on the project aims, the definition of MU, consent form and, eventually, the MU combination so far identified. Where applicable, pre-compiled AF sheets will be sent to the interviewee illustrating some preliminary results of the desk research. This will facilitate the interviews and address issues and knowledge gaps relevant for the analysis of MU potentials.

A local workshop within the last two months of the activity, focusing on an in depth analysis of the DABI derived from the desk research and interviews, will be performed, with particular focus on local/regional administrative, regulatory, socio-economic, environmental and technical constrains of the identified MU potentials. If needed, DABI scoring will be performed during the workshop and further discussed in detail taking into account the stakeholders perception on the issue.

The most suitable strategy for stakeholder engagement at workshop level will be identified, by considering the amount and type of stakeholders involved in the engagement process.

9. Details on stakeholder engagement:

As mentioned in section 8, the stakeholder engagement strategy will be developed upon interviews and local workshop. Interviews will take place in-situ, if possible during workshops/conferences and other type of meetings. If required, other engagement methods such as phone calls and teleconferences will be applied. The engagement plan foresees one stakeholder workshop in the last two months of the activity.

10. Expected results and impacts:

With this case study we want to discuss and agree on a definition of multi-use in the north Adriatic Sea and engage stakeholders in an active discussion on drivers and barriers related to multi-use in the area; the exercise will produce a concrete identification of areas where MU is more likely to have the maximum positive effect, as well as proposals on how to promote blue economy in the area and discussion on added values and negative impacts concerning environmental, socio-economic and technical aspects of multi-uses in the case study. These activities will be useful to also increase awareness of the issue of multi-use in the sea and its added value and positive effects among stakeholders.

Based on the case study results, scenarios for concrete MU will be developed and reviewed through the stakeholder engagement strategy.

Finally, the case study will provide elements and ideas for the development of the Action Plans (WP4) and can be used as initial step for the application of similar methodologies in other areas.

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2.7 Case study 7: Tourism & fisheries & energy production in the Aegean Sea

1. Case study n. 7
2. Regional Sea: Mediterranean Sea
3. Location: Mediterranean Sea: Aegean Sea / Cyclades
4. Title: Tourism & fisheries & energy production in the Aegean Sea
5. Study area:

6. Stakeholder identification:

a) Representatives of:

- Private sector (especially those who are directly involved in the MUs that will be explored)
- Those to be affected including the general public
- Local administration
- Relevant ministries
- NGOs
- Researchers with knowledge on the topic and the legal, technical, socioeconomic and ecological aspects of the MU scenario(s)

Depending on their background, most of these people may also be regarded as experts on legal, economic, environmental, licensing, spatial requirements and restrictions.

b) There will be a total of ~ 10 to 30 stakeholders, depending on the representativeness of key players

7. Issues to discuss with stakeholders:

Issues to be discussed with stakeholders can be grouped into four steps:

1st Stakeholders' perceptions on the barriers / drivers / added value / impacts that have already been established during the desk research for the specific MU issue will be explored, followed by the DABI scoring process described in the WP2 AF. Stakeholder views will also be gathered on other

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types of MUs, that may emerge as more appropriate for this case study.
 2nd Stakeholders'/experts' will be asked to describe what other DABI exist that were not covered in step 1.

3rd - Different MU scenarios will be explored (e.g., deliberative Multi Criteria Analysis (MCA) based on the weight different stakeholders put on specific criteria e.g. social equity, environmental sustainability, economic efficiency or other/supplementary criteria suggested by stakeholders)

4th - The majority's preference (emerging views and suggestions from stakeholders) will be compared and analysed to formulate potential solutions that will be identified based on a decision method (e.g. MCA, cooperative game theory (CGT), etc.) and further elaborate on that through stakeholder participation

8. Stakeholder engagement methods:

Semi-structured questionnaires will be used during face-to-face interviews or will be distributed via-mail/ post to collect info as described. Using these two methods we aspire to also collect information from experts, as a result there will be no need for expert panels to be used. Furthermore local workshops and/or consensus conferences may be organised for further elaboration on the third and fourth steps (see above) and for dissemination purposes.

9. Details on stakeholder engagement:

- The collection of information, the evaluation exercise and the elaboration on alternative scenarios will take place between July and September 2017.
- The number of participants will be in the range of 10 to 30 depending on representation of key actors. We aspire to engage the same stakeholders in all steps and in all methods per step outlined above.
- Presentations from the HCMR and other experts will take place during workshops or conferences.
- Preparation materials may include an introductory text accompanying the questionnaires (e.g. an initial conflict analysis), presentations and videos to accompany guidelines on what the participants are expected to do, during workshops and conferences.

10. Expected results and impacts:

Objectives:

- Data collection, identification of potential MUs and evaluation of MUs based on stakeholder's preferences
- Enhancement of communication and collaboration using meetings/workshops

Methods:

- Establishment of a mailing list and/or a group on social media to provide update on and make exchange of information on current and future initiatives accessible and visible
- Provision of project leaflets to the stakeholders that they can distribute during current or future events
- Distribution of e-newsletters

Stakeholder engagement process will be dynamic, iterative and adaptive. Accessibility to information and knowledge is a key issue amongst the case study's stakeholders and the ad hoc web-based dialogue platform that will be set up in the framework of WP5 will serve as a local hub for stakeholders, particularly the wider public, to collaborate, exchange information and knowledge through (and beyond) the project's life.

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